

Next Chapter – Tattoo & Piercing is situated in the heart of Morden, South West London. It was built as a point of reference for all those who are looking for a friendly and professional tattoo and piercing studio. It's conveniently located just a short walk away from the Morden Underground Station. They love giving all tattoo lovers a wider range of styles [Tattoo and piercing shop](#) from Neo Traditional tattoos, New School tattoos, Black and Grey/Colour realism tattoos to Dotwork Tattoos. Their artists are always enthusiastic about creating new custom tattoos and completely unique tattoo designs upon request. Walk-ins and appointments are always welcome. They are happy to cover all of your piercing needs as well. You can also find jewellery, books, gadgets, and after-care products at their studio. For any questions regarding tattoos or piercings please do not hesitate to contact them. Visit the Next Chapter – Tattoo & Piercing website at <https://www.nextchaptertattoo.com> You will be happy that you did!

Now that you know more about Next Chapter – Tattoo & Piercing, let's talk about why people love tattoos so much. There is no definitive answer to the question, "Why do people love tattoos so much?" But there are several reasons that people have chosen to add ink to their bodies. These are the most common:

Defying Culture and Family Expectations:

For many people, getting a tattoo is a way to defy cultural and family expectations that they may not want to face. They might get one to make a statement about how they disagree with a certain label that has been given to them by their family or that they are willing to challenge in a professional setting. It may also be a sign of rebellion against a particular religion or culture they are leaving behind. This is especially true if their old beliefs and values prohibit or frown on tattooed skin.

Choosing Designs that Show Off Their Personality:

Some people choose tattoos to show off their personality, whether it's something funny or outlandish or just a symbol of something significant to them. These individuals don't want to blend in or be like the rest of the kitchen utensil people that surround them, so they need a way to be seen as a distinct individual. These people also tend to have high self-esteem and a desire for self-expression. They want to have a piece of art on their body that they can be proud of and that they can look at whenever they need to feel a little extra confident. They want to be different and stand out from the crowd, so they choose designs that are bold and prominent. They want to be the person they always wanted to be, and tattoos are a way to achieve this goal.

Taking Risks:

When it comes to tattooing, there is no guarantee that the artist will do a great job. This is because it takes skill to design a tattoo that will be readable and not have any negative implications for your health, for this reason we've made a great recommendation with Next Chapter – Tattoo & Piercing. There are risks, too, of infection and disease, which can be dangerous if they are not treated properly. The dangers can come from sharing needles or ink or using an unsterilized tattoo studio. If a tattoo isn't right for you, or you want to change it, then getting it removed may be the best option. Luckily, there are some ways that you can do this and avoid complications or a costly re-tattoo.

It can also help to take some time to think about what you want the tattoo to mean, and make sure it fits your overall sense of style. This can be important because it will affect the design and size of the tattoo you get, if you decide to have one. Now that you know more about why people like tattoos so much, it is time to go back to the website of Next Chapter – Tattoo & Piercing and book an appointment today!